

THE IMPORTANCE OF XORAZM DUTOR MAQOMS IN UZBEK MUSICAL ART

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Abstract: This article scientifically analyzes the stages of formation and development of Xorazm dutar maqoms. The historical development of the Xorazm maqom school, the role of the dutar in maqom performance, and performance traditions are highlighted. In addition, the musical and stylistic features of dutar maqoms, the master-apprentice tradition, and their significance in modern performance practice are discussed. The study also emphasizes the importance of preserving and developing the national musical heritage.

Keywords: Xorazm maqom, dutar, maqom art, dutar maqoms, performance tradition, master-apprentice school, national music, folk instruments, musical heritage, traditional performance.

Uzbek national musical heritage has deep historical roots formed over many centuries. One of the highest examples of national music is maqom art. Maqom art occupies a special place as a unique classical heritage that embodies the artistic thinking, aesthetic views, and spiritual world of the people.

“Maqom art has a centuries-old history. This history can be divided into two major periods that differ from each other. The first period includes the study of the ancient origins of maqoms and their earliest melodic layers from the perspective of space and time¹”.

“Maqoms exist in the musical heritage of many Eastern nations. They form the basis of the national musical heritage of these peoples. Maqoms possess both theoretical and practical foundations and represent the masterful style of musical art among these nations²”.

The maqom art, which has been formed and perfected over centuries, is not only a supreme example of musical art but also an expression of the historical memory and national values of the people. In Uzbek musical culture, maqom art is characterized by the formation of the master-apprentice tradition. In particular, Shashmaqom, Xorazm maqoms, and the Fergana-Tashkent maqom paths have played a significant role in the development of national art as the main directions of Uzbek classical music. These maqom traditions are distinguished by their complex melodic systems, rich tonal possibilities, and deep philosophical meanings.

Especially, the Xorazm maqom traditions stand out due to their rich performance style, complex melodic structures, and features reflecting the national spirit.

“The part of Uzbek classical music associated with Xorazm is considered one of the richest and most meaningful components of this vast heritage. It is well known that Xorazm played a leading role in the formation of Uzbek statehood³”. In the development of this art, the dutar instrument has occupied an important place, functioning not only as an accompanying instrument but also as an independent performance medium.

“There are many types of plucked musical instruments in Uzbekistan. Among them, the most widespread is the dutar. The strings of the dutar are made of silk and are loosely stretched near the neck. Therefore, the sound of the dutar is not very loud. “Among Uzbek musical

¹ O.Ibrohimov, “Maqom asoslari”, T.: “Donishmand ziyosi” 2023, 5-bet

² I.Rajabov, “Maqom asoslari”, T.: “Yangi asr avlodi” 2019, 19-bet

³ Rtveldze E, Роль Хорезма в формировании государственности Узбекистана/ O‘zbekiston davlatchiligining shakllanishida Xorazmning o‘rni, T.: 2014

instruments, the dutar is the only instrument that not only allows the performance of two-voiced music but also makes such two-voiced performance obligatory”⁴.

Xorazm dutar maqoms embody the centuries-old musical thinking, aesthetic views, and performance traditions of the people. The formation process of these maqoms is closely connected with historical, cultural, and creative factors, and they have been transmitted from generation to generation through the master-apprentice tradition.

“Xorazm dutar maqoms are one of the most ancient and distinctive branches of the Xorazm classical music school, mainly formed on the basis of dutar performance practice. According to scholarly sources, the dutar was initially the primary instrument for maqom performance in Xorazm, and later it was enriched with tanbur and other instruments.”

Today, issues related to the preservation and development of the national musical heritage have become especially important. In this regard, it is one of the essential tasks to scientifically study Xorazm dutar maqoms, examine their stages of development, and determine their place in modern performance practice.

“Dutar maqoms are essentially a separate category compared to Shashmaqom and the Six-and-a-Half Maqoms. In the true sense, dutar maqoms represent an ‘open system’ that serves as an alternative to them. They also possess their own internal traditions and rules, but these are implemented more freely in comparison with Shashmaqom and the Six-and-a-Half Maqoms”. The Xorazm maqom school is considered one of the ancient musical traditions of Central Asia. Folk oral creativity, palace culture, and local performance traditions played an important role in the formation of this school. The dutar, as one of the widely распространенных string instruments in the Xorazm region, was actively used in maqom performance. Historical sources indicate that the dutar initially developed as an instrument for performing simple folk melodies and later became integrated into maqom performance.

Particularly in the Xorazm region, dutar performance developed unique stylistic features, which also influenced the performance style of maqoms. Master musicians made a great contribution to the formation of Xorazm dutar maqoms. They enriched maqom paths and created new performance methods. As a result, dutar maqoms became widely developed not only among the people but also within the sphere of professional musical art. “Another distinctive feature of dutar maqoms is their simplicity and syncretic character. By syncretism, it is meant that melody, poetry, and dance art are presented in an interconnected form.”

In conclusion, maqom art is considered one of the most unique and ancient layers of Uzbek national musical culture. It embodies the artistic thinking, spiritual values, and aesthetic views that have been formed over centuries. Maqoms occupy a special place in national musical art due to their complex melodic structures, deep philosophical meanings, and high performance traditions. Especially, Xorazm maqoms are recognized as an important component of Uzbek classical music because of their unique performance style, emotional melodies, and rich instrumental traditions. Maqom art is important not only as a musical heritage but also in educating the younger generation in the national spirit, shaping their aesthetic taste, and contributing to their spiritual development.

Today, the scientific study, preservation, and transmission of maqom art to future generations remain among the most urgent tasks. Therefore, maqom art continues to be cherished as a priceless treasure of Uzbek national culture.

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⁴ I.A.Akbarov, “O‘zbek xalq musiqasi” III tom (To‘plovchi va notaga oluvchi Yu.Rajabiy), T.: 1959, 7-bet

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